

samples were washed with distilled water till pH of the wash-liquid was 0.5-1.5 pH higher than the required sample pH, and the wash-liquid was free from the leached-out acid or alkali. The significant variance in pH of the wash-liquid and the prepared aluminas indicates surface hydrolytic-type reactions :

Hydrated ions

In case of the wash-liquid, the backward reaction operates, and equilibrium is not established, which results in a different pH of the liquid.

Solutes :

The dyes orange 'G' (BDH) and Lissamine Green BN (Chroma) were repeatedly crystallised from ethanol-water (1 : 1, v/v), and dried at 80° for 24 hr. From the stock solution in water (0.2g/l), 2.5-100 ml solutions were withdrawn, diluted to 100 ml (except 100 ml solution), and estimated at 472 (OG) and 610 (LG) nm respectively with Spekol spectrophotometer (Carl Zeiss, No. 376626, accuracy $\pm 0.5\%$).

Adsorption experiments were conducted by equilibrating alumina (0.25 g) with the dye solutions of known concentration in 25 ml-volumetric flasks. Periodical shaking was made, and after a specified period, 2 ml of the aliquot withdrawn, centrifuged and estimated.

Adsorption vs Time and Temperature :

The variation of adsorption from aq. solutions as a function of time (10 min-120 hr) at $30 \pm 1^\circ$ was studied using alumina of pH 3.5-7.0. The dyes show fast adsorption, and only in 10 min 95% (OG) and 65% (LG) adsorption occurs at pH 3.0-4.0. However, the rate is slow for alumina of pH > 4.0, and equilibrium is attained in 24 hrs. The temperature-effect studies (30°-60°) with alumina of pH 4.0-7.5 show athermic nature (40°-60°) but endothermic behaviour is shown by LG at 30°-40°. Giles *et al*° have also reported the endothermic nature of LG at 30°-42°. For OG, the adsorption is exothermic in the range 30°-40°. However, the changes are so small that heat of adsorption could not be calculated.

Adsorption vs pH :

The results of change in the nature of adsorption with pH are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. It is observed that the affinity of the solutes for the substrates gradually increases with decrease in pH of the substrates. Quantitative adsorption occurs at pH 3.5-4.0 (OG) and pH 3.5-4.5 (LG). The process drops to zero at pH 9.5 and 10.0 for OG and LG respectively.

Fig. 1. Change in the nature of adsorption of orange 'G' from aqueous solutions on alumina of varying pH. (Time : 24 hr ; Temperature : $30 \pm 1^\circ$)

Fig. 2. Change in the nature of adsorption of Lissamine green 'BN' from aqueous solutions on alumina of varying pH.

(Time : 24 hr ; Temperature : $30 \pm 1^\circ$)

Desorption Studies :

The degree of reversibility of sorption of the dyes adsorbed from aq. solutions on alumina ($30 \pm 1^\circ$, 24 hr, pH 3.5-7.5) was studied with a number of organic solvent-water mixtures and aq. inorganic electrolytes (M/100 NaCl, Na_2SO_4 and Na_3PO_4) at $30 \pm 1^\circ$.

The study reveals that the dyes are completely desorbed with pyridine-water (1:4, v/v), aq. Na_2SO_4 and aq. Na_3PO_4 . LG adsorbed at pH 3.5, however, could not be desorbed with Na_2SO_4 . Aq. NaCl is ineffective in desorbing LG but OG adsorbed at pH 3.0, 6.0, 6.5 and 7.0 could be desorbed to the extent of 40%, 50%, 75% and cent percent respectively. The dye at pH 3.5 could not be desorbed with the electrolyte.

Results and Discussion

The dyes investigated are the sodium salts of sulphonated aromatic compounds, such as Na^+D^- . OG is an anionic dye, wholly acid (no basic side chain) and LG is a weakly amphoteric dye⁷. The acid-treated alumina may adsorb the anionic dyes by ion-exchange of single dye-anions or aggregated dye-anions (micelles) or through covalent bond formation with anionic groups (e.g., sulphonate) of the dyes.

The ion-exchange is shown by :

- (i) The greater degree of adsorption in a short time-interval and athermic nature of the process. The apparent endothermic nature ($30^\circ\text{-}40^\circ$) has been attributed to the aggregation of the dyes in solution⁶.

- (ii) *Reversibility of Adsorption :*

The present trend to define ion-exchange is for the processes which are truly chemically reversible⁸. The desorption characteristics with the inorganic electrolytes (Na_2SO_4 and Na_3PO_4) show quantitative desorption, pointing to ion-exchange nature of the process. The inorganic anions, it appears, probably compete with the dye-anions at the film surface for the ionic sites. It was also observed that in the presence of these desorbents (1.0 ml, M/100), adsorption of the dyes is retarded greatly, and in the presence of PO_4^{3-} ions, adsorption of the solutes does not occur. It is likely that at low pH values, a primary reaction of the type shown below may occur :

Irreversibility of the dyes at pH 3.5, probably involves strong negatively-charged complexes.

Potentiometric titration studies of the Cl^- ions released after adsorption of the dyes on alumina (pH 3.5-6.5) showed an increase in the concentration of chloride ions at pH < 5.0. However, no change could be detected on the substrates of pH > 5.0.

Desorption with pyridine-water is rather difficult to explain at this stage. Certain studies⁸ suggest disaggregation of dyes in presence of basic substances like pyridine, urea, dimethyl formamide which form an adduct or complex. The desorbed LG with pyridine-water, even on treatment with buffers, could not be estimated at 630 nm.

- (iii) *pH and Adsorption :*

At pH < 4.5, the dyes are adsorbed cent-percent which decreases with increase in pH. The ionically-bound chloride content of alumina appears to decrease continuously with increasing pH, becoming essentially negligible in basic solutions. It appears that rapid exchange of the dye anions occurs at pH < 4.5 followed by a slow exchange at sites within the alumina at pH > 4.5. The slow inward-diffusion into the micropores of the substrates at higher pH (pH > 4.5) may cause long equilibration period of the dyes.

At high pH values, the H^+ ions of the >Al-OH of the substrates tend to dissociate from the oxygen, leaving a negative charge on the surface. As the pH is lowered, additional H^+ may associate with the $-\text{OH}$, leaving a net positive charge, which will attract the dye anions.

Conclusion :

The study shows that selectivity of the anionic dyes is strongly dependent on pH of the substrates, and hence certain separations should be possible. In practice we found so, and the two dyes were separated on an alumina column of pH 4.5.

References

1. K. A. KRAUS, H. O. PHILLIPS, T. A. CARLSON and J. S. JOHNSON, *Proc. 2nd U. N. Intern. Conf. Peaceful uses, Geneva, 1958, 28, 3.*
2. C. B. AMPHLETT, L. A. McDONALD AND M. J. REDMAN, *Chem. and Ind. (London), 1957, 365.*
3. G. L. MUNDHARA and J. S. TIWARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc., 1978, 55, 1039.*

4. D. J. O'CONNOR, A. S. BUCHANAN and P. G. JOHNSON, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1956, **50**, 229.
5. M. J. FULLER, *Chromatographic Rev.*, 1971, **14**, 45.
6. C. H. GILES, J. J. GRECZEK and S. N. NAKHWA, *J. Chem. Soc. (London)*, 1961, 93.
7. E. GURR, "*Synthetic Dyes in Biology, Medicine and Chemistry*", Academic Press, 1971, 260 & 404.
8. C. H. GILES, A. P. D'SILVA and A. S. TRIVEDI, *J. Appl. Chem. (London)*, 1970, **20**, 87.